

LANGUAGE OF TELEVISION AND RADIO BROADCASTS: FUNCTIONS, FEATURES. NORMS AND DEVIATIONS OF SPEECH CULTURE

Eshankulov Hamrakul Mamatkulovich

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University Associate Professor

Abstract: *In our dynamic and very demanding times, a modern person, in order to achieve his goals and objectives, must have not only professional qualities, but also have clear and normative speech. Literary language is considered the basis of speech culture, as it corresponds to the norms of the modern Russian language. The article characterizes the concept of “speech culture”; the norms of literary language are considered; The most common errors of deviation from literary norms are given.*

Key words and phrases: *literary language; National language; language norm; communication culture; oral speech; written language; error.*

The current stage of development of society, which is undergoing economic processes of globalization, integration, the introduction of the principles of the Bologna system of education in Russian universities, which entailed the internationalization of education, the rapid pace of change in socio-economic living conditions and the aggravation of national contradictions, the increase in volumes of information, the introduction of communication technologies, has led to one of the first places is the problem of communication culture, which is the basis of interpersonal relationships in a changing world in which every person strives to be successful. Success largely depends on the person himself: on the level of culture of oral and written speech; speech science concepts and improvement of communicative and speech skills; the ability to make a first impression (appearance - hairstyle, clothing and jewelry - indicates success and respectability). “The appearance... must correspond to the situation and the nature of communication, the tastes of the audience and not distract the attention of the listeners” [14, p. 43]. Except

Moreover, the first impression of a person is usually formed on the basis of the speech culture demonstrated by the interlocutor. A person’s speech culture, the ability to logically express his thoughts and feelings both orally and in writing are his calling card. It has been proven that people who can speak well and beautifully will be able to achieve significant results due to their almost unique ability to speak in public. In this regard, some people can be listened to for a long time without being distracted, while others are difficult to listen to completely, because there is an irresistible desire to

immediately end the communication process. In addition, the ability to speak is the main indicator that distinguishes a person from an animal.

Speech skill is the ability to choose the most successful one from possible options, observing language norms, to express thoughts and attitudes. We emphasize that the ability to competently and concisely present information, timely and correctly respond to changes in the mood and thoughts of the interlocutor(s) contributes not only to adequate interaction between individuals, but also to the consolidation of society as a whole. In this regard, a person with a culture of communication becomes in demand in modern realities. This is especially clearly seen in professions for which knowledge of the modern Russian literary language is an integral component, in particular for diplomats, lawyers, radio and television presenters, journalists, teachers and managers at various levels. However, not only business and public people, but also those whose work activities are directly related to human resources should master the basics of cultural speech. Thus, the culture of speech acquires special importance for teachers and teachers, since they give a start in life to the younger generation. Thus, the skill is correct (in compliance with the norms and patterns

Russian literary language) to build your oral statement, to convincingly defend your own position is necessary for everyone who finds themselves in the mainstream of the modern whirlpool of life.

It should be noted that the modern Russian literary language occupies a central place in the basis of speech culture, since the use of literary language norms ensures the selection and organization of linguistic means that allow, in a specific speech situation, to ensure the desired effect in achieving the set communicative goals. In this regard, the ability to clearly and accurately formulate goals, substantiate them, put forward and defend ideas, and establish verbal contact is very important and in demand in the communication process. In addition, it is appropriate to emphasize that in the process of communication one can observe certain inaccuracies in speech, relating, in particular, to the use of certain words and expressions, emphasis, etc. This is evidence that a person has not fully mastered the norms of the modern Russian literary language.

In addition, “a typical error in speech is tautology - repetition of words of the same root or similar sound in a sentence, for example: “Regarding this point, the following should be noted.” Unfortunately, tautology is very common in speech, for example: “plan a plan”; “the following should be noted”; “recorded in the protocol”, etc.

Let’s not ignore pleonastic expressions. Pleonasm is a semantic redundancy that is unacceptable from the point of view of the modern Russian language. Below are typical pleonastic expressions: gesticulate with hands, work colleague, go back, overall dimensions, palms of hands, month of March. Note that among pleonasms there are

exceptions that are acceptable and included in the category of scientific terms, for example, second-hand book, money, information message, exhibits, etc.

An inept choice of linguistic means can lead to the appearance of stylistic defects in oral speech and writing. “Most often in speech there are stylistic errors that are the result of a deviation from the principle of appropriateness, for example: “My brother got it into his head that he would be a pilot.” The next type of stylistic error is verbosity, which is the result of a deviation from the principle of brevity of speech, for example: “Cedars are not uncommon in our taiga. They are found quite often.” Stylistic errors can currently be understood as certain speech disorders that arise as a result of stylistic diversity, disunity in the use of stylistically colored means. Thus, in a literary context, the use of slang, colloquial and abusive language is inappropriate, and in official business speech colloquial and expressive words should be avoided.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Vvedenskaya L. A., Pavlova L. G., Kataeva E. Yu. Russian language. A culture of speech. Business conversation. M.: Knorus, 2014. 424 p.

2. Vereshchagin E. M., Kostomarov V. G. Language and culture. M.: Indrik, 2005. 1038 p.

3. Levchaeva N.V. Business style: features of the use of communicative qualities of speech in the texts of documents // XI Derzhavin readings in the Republic of Mordovia: materials of the All-Russian. scientific-practical conf. Saransk: ExYuksPraktik, 2015. pp. 197-200.

4. Levchaeva N.V. Public speaking as an effective means of improving the quality of student learning // World of Science and Education. 2015. No. 1. P. 39-43.